

Analysis Strategic of Ticket Purchase at Traveloka in Pangkalan Kerinci City Communities

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ARTICLE INFO :

Keywords :

Trust; Customer Reviews; Customer Ratings; and Purchase Decisions

Article History :

Received :2023-10-10

Revised : 2023-12-01

Accepted :2023-12-30

Online :2023-12-30

ABSTRACT

The study is aimed at determining the influence of Trust, Customer Review, and Customer Rating on Buying Interest. The population of the study is a community of Kerinci Base City and the sampling method used in this study is non-probability sample. Primary and secondary data are used for analysis. The analysis was done with double linear regression and SPSS 25 program. The results of the research show that the Trust, Customer Review, and Customer Rating variables have a significant influence on Buy Interest in part, while the f test shows that the trust, customer review, and customer rating variables simultaneously exert a significant impact on buy interest, with the R square of 0.612. This shows that overall, the Trust variables, customer reviews and customer ratings exert significant influences on Buying Interest.

INTRODUCTION

Traveloka is one of the most popular online travel agencies in Indonesia. Traveloka is a leading technology company in Southeast Asia, providing a way for users to obtain and book a variety of transportation products, financial services, lifestyle activities, and accommodation. As a super lifestyle app in South East Asia, Traveloka has a comprehensive product portfolio, including transportation services such as train tickets, buses, planes, car rental, airport transfers, and the largest inventory access accommodation in South Eastern Asia, including homestays, hotels, hostels, apartments, bungalows, villas, and resorts, making Traveloka the booking platform of choice as the most complete accommodation package.

Based on traffic data accessed at www.similarweb.com, year2022 explains that Traveloka.com's visitors in October were 15.6 million, in November 16.8 million, and in December 18.9 million. Based on the Playstore rating, Traveloka.com has the highest number of stars on the playstore app, with 4.8, followed by Agoda.com with 4.7, Airpaz.com 4.5, Tiket.com 4.5 and Airasia.com 3.8.

According to (Ichsan et al., 2018) one of the points of view that influence consumer desire to buy is online consumer reviews and ratings. Buying interest is formed on the basis of the occurrence of alternative assessment procedures that are in the assessment procedure. Purchase interest is based on the value of the product that has been considered, the profit obtained more than the contribution to acquire, with the purchase incentive increasing. In contrast, the benefit is less than the sacrifice, generally consumer refuses to buy and usually turns away from the similar product.

Trust is the seriousness of the provider of a product or service that can be gained in the form of such behavior in the long term to satisfy the desire of the consumer. Trust or trust It is a belief that consumers have in considering buying a product or service. According to (Auliya et al, 2017) customer review is an assessment given to consumers that refers to information from product assessment in various perspectives, using this information, consumers can evaluate the quality of the product or service they are looking for through the assessment and knowledge expressed by consumers who have made purchases of products or services from online stores.

According to Lackermair in (Istiqomah, 2020) consumer ratings are basically the same as reviews or reviews, but the ratings submitted by consumers are stars. The more stars, the better the rating of the provider of

the product or service. A star scale or rating usually consists of one to five stars and is the determinant of whether or not a marketplace.

Trust or trust is an important thing that is influential in business, especially in the field of services. If trust in a service already exists, then the greater interest of consumers to make purchases. A trust can be gained from a variety of factors, including reviews and ratings. Having good reviews from other consumers on a service, it can increase consumer confidence. Similarly, with a rating, the higher the rating, then the higher is the confidence that consumers have in the service. If a business has already gained confidence, good reviews and high ratings, then it is highly likely that the consumer is interested in making a purchase.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Purchase Decision

According to (Kotler and Armstrong, 2008: 181), stating that "a purchase decision is a buyer's decision about which brand to buy." In a purchase decision, there are two factors that emerge between the intention to buy and the purchase decision. Private and Irawan (2008:145) in (Sandy Sinambow and Irvan Trang,2015: 302) put forward consumer decisions are motives or incentives arising against something where a buyer makes a purchase because of a need and desire.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012:149) in (Ari wibowo, 2014:4-5) stated that, "Purchase decision is the buyer's decision about which brand to buy" which means that a purchase decision is a stage of the decision process in which consumers actually make a purchase of a product.

Indicators of purchasing decisions according to (Kotler and Armstrong, 2008: 181):

1. Identification of needs;
2. Information;
3. Evaluation;
4. Drinking Decisions;
5. Post-purchase behaviour

B. Trust

According to (Sumarwan, 2011), trust is the consumer's understanding of a service, attribute, and utility. Based on this response, consumer understanding is not separate from consumer knowledge because consumer knowing is consumer trust. A trust is a consumer's knowledge of a product or service that can be trusted for its benefits and usefulness, and guarantees that it is in accordance with the expectations of the consumer.

According to (Ardialis & Hayani, 2022) There are three factors that affect consumer confidence, namely, First, facing those related to the work done by the organization, in relation to business and company achievements in the monetary field, etc. The company will have a better understanding of the wishes and needs of its customers because of its extensive experience and interest in the business. Second, the quality of work, especially the company's procedures and results, can be evaluated by the customer or the community. Quality confidence will be produced from unlimited high-quality work.

Djamil (2023) Third, intelligence is an organization's capacity to deal with internal problems. Intelligence can also build trust because high credibility can't increase customer confidence if it's not based on intelligence in attracting customers.

Factors that can influence trust or trust according to Wiethoff in (Mercy, 2014) are:

1. Personality preposition. Indicates the level of preposition of an individual in the creation of a trust, in which the preposition of each individual is different from that of each other to believe in the other individual. The higher the rate of individual preposition to the trust, the greater the expectation to be trusted by another individual.
2. Reputation plays an important role in giving trust because the reputation of others will realize a firm hope to bring the individual to the element of trust and mistrust is also very likely to create a relationship approach to trusting each other.
3. Actual experience. Actual experiences in individuals include building facets of experience to speak, work, coordinate and communicate. The element of trust and mistrust defines a relationship through the domination of an experience in which an individual is inclined to generalize a relationship from the highest or lower element of faith or mistrust.

The psychological orientation of the individual is influenced by the relationship formed or otherwise which means that the individual begins to build relationships that match their soul so that their orientation remains consistent that includes in social relationships.

C. Costumer Review

According to (Auliya el al, 2017) customer review is an assessment given to consumers that refers to information from the product assessment in various perspectives, using this information, consumers can evaluate the quality of the product or service sought through the assessment and knowledge expressed by consumers who have made purchases of products or services from online stores.

According to (Mo, Li, Fan, 2015) Customer Review is information from product or service reviews generated by consumers published on third-party websites and retailers. Using this information, a buyer is able to conclude the advantage of a product or services based on the judgment and experience of other buyers.

Factors – Factors Affecting Customer Reviews, according to (Hidayati, 2018) factors –21 Customer reviews are:

1. Evaluation of the product given by the consumer after the purchase.
2. Consistency of reviews given by other consumers.
3. Compatibility of product information with consumer knowledge.
4. Complete reviews of other consumers that influence in product determination.
5. Interested in buying the product.

D. Costumer Rating

According to (Auliya et al, 2017) Customer Rating is a scale that reveals consumer opinions, the rating scale in online marketplaces is to give a star scale. The higher the number of stars, the higher the rating of a product or service. The rating is delivered by consumers who have already purchased and then posted on the web or booth merchant. Rating is a way for consumers to give feedback to a product or service provider.

While according to Lackermair in (Istiqomah, 2020) consumer ratings are basically the same as reviews or reviews, but the ratings submitted by consumers are stars. The more stars, the better the rating of the provider of the product or service. A star scale or rating usually consists of one to five stars and determines whether a marketplace is good or not.

Affecting Customer Rating Factors, aAccording to (Tantrabundit, 2019) there are three factors that influence customer rating:

1. Information accuracy means that if the customer provides the correct information about a product, it can help other consumers find the information they want about the product.
2. As a reference to the product, the consumer can use the information through the rating as an instrumental reference in order to see what is popular with the other consumer for their own preference.
3. Product quality means that consumers will give a high rating if the quality of the product is good and corresponds to what is desired by consumers, in the same way consumers would give a low rating if product quality is bad or not in accordance with the wishes of consumers.

E. Conceptual Framework

Gambar 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

A. Population and Sampling Research.

Djamil (2023) The population in this study is the population of the community of the base city of Pangkalan Kerinci who has made purchases in the Traveloka application of which the number is unknown, Because the number of samples is uncertain, Irawan in (Sukandarrumidi and Hayanto, 2014) mentions that in order for the study to be well described, then the total sample scattered at least 30 respondents, but some recommend a total of at least 100 respondents. Therefore, in this study the sample is 100 respondents from the community of Pangkalan Kerinci City Base who have made purchases in traveloka

B. Data collection techniques

Interviews are used as data gathering techniques when researchers want to do preliminary studies to find a problem to be investigated, and also when they want to know things from respondents who are more in-depth and the number of respondents is small.

The likert scale is a scale designed to enable the respondent to answer different levels on each object to be measured. A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is done by giving a set of written questions to respondents to answer Documentation is a method used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, numerical writing and images that are reports and descriptions that can support research.

C. Data Analysis Methods

1. Descriptive Data Analysis

Sugiyono (2016) argues that the method of descriptif analysis is the statistical method used to analyze data by describing or describing the data collected without intending conclusions that apply to generality and generalization.

2. Quantitative Data Analysis

Sugiyono (2016:8) presented the method of quantitative research understood as a method of research based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research on a particular population or sample, the collection of data using the research instrument of data analysis is quantitatively/statistically, with the aim of testing the hypothesis that has been established.

D. Data Quality Test

The quality test of the instrument aims to determine the consistency and accuracy of the data collected. How the testing is carried out with the Validity Test and Reliability Test of data obtained through the respondent's questionnaire , A question is said to be reliable if a person's answer to a question is consistent or stable over time.

1. Validity Test

A validity test is used to measure the validity or non-validity of a questionnaire. The validity test can be performed by looking at the correlation between the scores of each item in the questionnaire and the total scores to be measured, i.e. by using the pearson coefficient in SPSS.

2. Reliability Test

The reliability test is used to determine the consistency and reliability of a measuring device, whether the measuring instrument will obtain a consistent measurement if measurements are repeated again. The reliability test in this study uses the Cronbach Alpha technique, and the value can be seen on the processing results using the SPSS program.

3. Classical Assumption Test

To determine whether a regression estimate is free of bias, which results in an invalid regression result and eventually the regression cannot be used as a basis for testing hypotheses and drawing conclusions, the classical assumption is used.

- a) Data Normality Test
The normality test is performed to test whether the data examined for the whole indicator and variable is normal.
- b) Multicollinearity test
The multicollinearity test is used to test whether in the regression model formed there is a high or perfect correlation between free variables or not.
- c) Autocorrelation Test
Autocorrelation is a correlation that occurs between members of a series of observations organized in times series at different times.
Autocorrelation aims to test whether in a linear regression there is a correlation between interference errors at the period t if there is an autocorrelation means.

E. Hypothesis Test

1. Partial Test

This test was performed at a significant rate of 5% and the degree of freedom (df) $n-k-1$ compared to the t-table. If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the independent variable has a meaningful influence on the dependent variable. On the contrary, when $t_{count} < t_{table}$ then H_0 is accepted. And H_a rejected means that the independent variable has no meaningful influence on the dependent variable.

2. Simultan Test

This test is used to determine the influence of joint free variables on bound variables. Where $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, or jointly the free variable can describe the bound variable simultaneously. On the other hand, when $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then H_0 is accepted, or jointly free variables can explain the bound variable concurrently.

3. Double Linear Analysis

This research uses quantitative descriptive methods, i.e. the data collected is analyzed by delineating and associating existing theories with existing problems, which will then provide relevant results for further conclusions and suggestions. To determine the magnitude of the influence of a variable, a double linear regression method is used to measure the relationship between a bound variable and two or more free variables.

RESULT

1. Validity Tests

Table 1. Validity Test

Item Pernyataan	Corrected item-total Correlation	Tanda	Korelasi	Keterangan
Trust (X1)				
X1.1	0,827	>	0,30	Valid
X1.2	0,823	>	0,30	Valid
X1.3	0,773	>	0,30	Valid
Customer Review (X2)				
X2.1	0,823	>	0,30	Valid
X2.2	0,834	>	0,30	Valid
X2.3	0,862	>	0,30	Valid
X2.4	0,862	>	0,30	Valid
X2.5	0,784	>	0,30	Valid
Customer Rating (X3)				
X3.1	0,787	>	0,30	Valid

X3.2	0,752	>	0,30	Valid
X3.3	0,778	>	0,30	Valid
X3.4	0,749	>	0,30	Valid
Strategic Decition Purchasing (Y)				
Y1	0,758	>	0,30	Valid
Y2	0,745	>	0,30	Valid
Y3	0,727	>	0,30	Valid
Y4	0,697	>	0,30	Valid

Source : Data SPSS 25, 2023

Based on the recapitulation of the validity test above, it can be stated that the measurement used in this study is valid or capable of measuring the phenomenon studied, with the result for each questionnaire statement per variable can be seen that the value of the Corrected item total correlation is greater than 0.30. This indicates that the data has met the validity test assumption and can be used for further regression analysis.

2. Reliability Tets

Table 2. Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Tanda	Nilai	Kesimpulan
<i>Trust (X1)</i>	0,726	>	0,60	Reliabel
<i>Customer Review (X2)</i>	0,890	>	0,60	Reliabel
<i>Customer Rating (X3)</i>	0,763	>	0,60	Reliabel
Minat Beli (Y)	0,710	>	0,60	Reliabel

Source: SPSS Process Data 25

Based on the test results of the measuring instrument used in this study, the value of cronbach's alpha obtained by processing using the help of SPSS 25 is above 0.60 so the instrument measuring instruments used in the study are considered reliable or consistent when used in several measurements.

3. Normality Test

Table 3. Normality Test

N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.38739148
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.062
	Positive	.062
	Negative	-.046
Test Statistic		.062
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

Source: SPSS Process Data 25

Based on the results of the normality test above, a significance value $> \alpha$ ($0,200 > 0,05$) is obtained so that it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

4. Multicollinority test

Table 4. Multicolinierity Test

Model		Unstandarized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	2.661	1.182		2.251	.027		
	Trust (X1)	.385	.092	.333	4.159	.000	.632	1.583
	Customer Review (X2)	.238	.050	.365	4.773	.000	.693	1.443
	Customer Rating (X3)	.267	.076	.264	3.487	.001	.705	1.418

a. Dependent Variable: Strategic Purchase Decision (Y)

Source: SPSS Process Data 25

Based on the data processing results in this study using SPSS 25, the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value produced in this test for Trust was 1,583, Customer Review was 1,443, and Customer Rating was 1,418. Thus, the value of VIF produced by each variable is less than 10, so it can be concluded on the regression model formed in the study there are no symptoms of multicollinearity VIF value generated. And in this study, only three variables were used.

5. Autokorelasi test

Table 5. Autocorelation Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.782 ^a	.612	.599	1.300	2.245

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Rating (X3), Customer Review (X2), Trust (X1)

b. Dependent Variable: Strategic Purchase Decision (Y)

Source: SPSS Process Data 25

Based on table 5.13 of the above values, it is known that the value dw (2,245) < 3. It shows that there is no autocorrelation either positive or negative in the model.

6. Coefisient

Table 6. Coefisient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.661	1.182		2.251	.027
	Trust (X1)	.385	.092	.333	4.159	.000
	Customer Review (X2)	.238	.050	.365	4.773	.000
	Customer Rating (X3)	.267	.076	.264	3.487	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Strategic Purchase Decision (Y)

Source: SPSS Process Data 25

in the regression equation is:

- The constant value (α) is 2,661. This means that if the Trust, Customer Review, and Customer Rating are assumed to be zero (0), then the Buy Interest is fixed to 2,661
- The regression coefficient value of 0.385 indicates that Trust (X1) has a 1 unit increase, then Trust will have a 0.385.
- The regression coefficient value of 0.238 indicates that Customer Review (X2) has an increase of 1 unit, then Customer Reviews will have an increase by 0.238.
- The regression coefficient value of 0.267 indicates that Customer Rating (X3) has increased 1 unit, then Customer Review will have increased by 0.267.
- Standard error (e) is a random variable and has a probability distribution that represents all factors that have an influence on Y but are not included in the equation.

7. T Test

Table 7. T Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.661	1.182		2.251	.027
	Trust (X1)	.385	.092	.333	4.159	.000
	Customer Review (X2)	.238	.050	.365	4.773	.000
	Customer Rating (X3)	.267	.076	.264	3.487	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Strategic Purchase Decision (Y)

Based on the tables of makadiatas can be known as follows:

- Trust variable (X1), known thitung (4,159) > ttable (1,984) and Sig 0,000 < 0.05. This means that the Trust has a significant influence on the Purchase Decision on Traveloka
- Variable Customer Review (X2), known thitung (4,773) > ttable (1,984) and Sig. 0,000 < 0,05. Means Customer Reviews have a significant influence on the purchase decision Traveloka has

- c. Customer Rating Variable (X3), known thitung (3,487) > ttable (1,984) and Sig. 0.001 < 0,05. This means that Customer Ratings have a significant influence on Traveloka's Purchase Decision

8. F Test

Table 8. F Test

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	255.466	3	85.155	50.387	.000 ^b
	Residual	162.244	96	1.690		
	Total	417.710	99			

Source: SPSS Process Data 25

From the above table it is known that F_{hitung} is 50,387 with a significant 0,000 and the number of statistical F_{table} is 2,699. Thus known F_{hitung} is $(50,387) > F_{\text{table}}$ (2,699) with a significance 0,000 < 0,05. This means that simultaneously or concurrently Trust, Customer Review, and Customer Rating have a significant influence on Traveloka's Purchase Decision.

CONCLUSION

- The Trust Variable has a positive and significant influence on the Buying Decision of Traveloka in Pangkalan Kerinci City
- The Customer Review Variable had a significant and positive influence upon the Purchase Decision on Traveloka at Pangkalan Kerinci City
- The Customers Rating Variable have a positive, significant influencing on the Customer Rating Decision at Traveloka in Pangkalan Kerinci City
- The Trust variable, customer review, customer rating as a whole had an influence of 61% on the Traveloka Shopping Decision in Pangkalan Kerinci City , while the remaining 39% were influenced by other variables not studied in this study.

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